

RAKTA MOKSHAN IN VICHARCHIKA

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INTRODUCTION

The disease Vicharchika has been dealt with in the ancient texts under the Kushtha Rogas. In total eighteen type of Kushtha rogas have been described in the texts. Regarding its treatment, both the schools, are in agreement that Rakta Mokshana should be the only remedy of it.

The term Rakta Mokshana is a procedure which can be achieved with the help of so many methods. Of these Leech application, for removing the vitiated blood tops the list of all the procedures.

Another indication regarding the Rakta mokshan is that it can cure all the diseases of the skin.

The disease Vicharchika has not been dealt with very widely in the texts, but in day-to-day practice is seen that quite a good

number of patients are suffering from this disease, On the other hand in the modern texts it is seen, that in spite of sufficient achievement in the medical science, no complete remedy has yet been evolved.

So far as the distress among the sufferers is concerned, it seems to be a real problem to manage, hence it was thought to work over the problem for a proper answer.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

All the patients were Selected from the Outpatient.

Leech application was selected for the present study, the reason being easy availability, safe to carry out the Procedure, and sufficient repeated advocacy of Leech application in skin diseases.

OBSERVATIONS

Total number of patients selected for the study was 30. Among them 21 were males and 9 females. Age ranging from 12 to 70. After completing the registration, every patient was put to Sweda Karma, which was done by formenting the parts with hot watar swabs for 30 minutes. Afterwards the fresh Nirvisha Leeches were applied to the diseased part; and it was allowed to suck the blood till it fell down itself. Then the area was cleaned and dressed with Shatdhatu Gritta.

The patients were asked to remain in the Rakta Mokshana Recovery room for sometime (for about 1/2 hour) to see the post leech application, bleeding or any other trouble.

In one sitting more than four were applied to the part depending on the surface area affected. The same procedure was repeated at alternate day.

COMPLICATIONS

Out of 30 patients 2 patients complained of itching during the leech application. One patient bled for more than 1/2 hour, and has to come back after 4 hours of the application, one patient developed severe itching and rashes 8 hours after the leech application.

RESULTS

The criteria of relief/cure was made on the basis of relief in the signs and symptoms. A complete data of 30 cured patients is given below regarding the age, total number of sitting,

total number of Leech application, total blood sucked Gul, total days taken for treatment, characters of Vitiated blood, chronicity and symptoms index.

Table: Number of patients for different groups.

Age		Total no. of sitting		Total no. of Leech applied			Total Blood sucked out in ml.		
12-30	31-70	2-10	11-22	4-20	21-100	101-130	30-100	101-200	201-320
16	14	24	6	12	10	8	7	14	8
Total days for treat.		Character of blood according to Prakriti			Chronicity			Symptoms index	
10-30	31-60	Kaph	Vat	Pitt	1 month to 1 yr	1 to 2 yr	2 to 15 year	6-15	16-25
22	8	19	4	7	20	6	4	12	18

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this Study the work, over the problem performed according to the directions able in Ayurvedic texts. But where no rticulary advice had been advocated, there No suitable ideas had been employed to develop the procedure, Regarding the number of sitting of Rakta Mokshan, it was considered observing the State of chronicity. The number of Leeches were being used, seeing the state of severity and area affected.